

ANALYSIS OF INTERFACE STRENGTH AND FAILURE MODE OF INDENTED SMA WIRE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The premise of normal serviceability of an adaptive deformable composite structure based on a Shape Memory Alloy (SMA) driver is that the interface performance is good. Studies have shown that the introduction of fine indentations on the round SMA wire can significantly improve the interface performance. Considering the more complex surface morphology of the indented SMA wire, the actual stress state at the interface with the substrate will be much more complicated than the smooth SMA wire. In this paper, through the cylindrical drawing test, based on the built-up bond-slip test system, the interface pull-slip data is collected. Combined with theoretical analysis, the bond-slip constitutive model of the interface is derived, and the critical failure stress is compared with the experimental and numerical simulation and theoretical calculation results.

1 INTRODUCTION

Adaptive morphing structures are receiving more and more attention due to their huge potential value. Because Shape Memory Alloy drives have large driving force, simple triggering mode and easy to be embedded in the composite matrix, it is an ideal driving material for adaptive deformation structure. Therefore, after Rogers and Robertshaw^[1-2] first introduced the concept of SMA Hybrid Composites (SMAHC) in 1988, the research on SMAHC-based adaptive deformation structure scheme has become a hot spot. However, the practical application of SMAHC on the "adaptive deformation" structure has not progressed so far. The main reason is that the interface performance between SMA fiber and composite matrix is poor. Therefore, how to improve the interface performance has become a hot research direction.

Currently, methods such as acid etching, manual sanding, sandblasting, mechanical twisting, silane coupling agent coating, and nano-silica surface treatment^[3-10] have been proposed to improve the interfacial properties of SMA filaments. Comparing the "mechanical indentation method" proposed by the research group, the operation is simple, the cost is low, and the reinforcing effect is remarkable. However, the introduction of the interface constitutive structure after indentation is still lack of in-depth study. The interface constitutive of the SMA wire is still lack of evidence, and it is necessary to carry out targeted research.

In this paper, the bond-slip test system is built by the cylindrical drawing test, and the interface bond slip data is collected. Combined with the theoretical analysis, the slip initial load and the initial failure strength of the interface are obtained, and the bond-slip constitutive model of the interface is established. The model is constructed and the critical failure stress is compared with the results of experimental and numerical simulations and theoretical calculations to guide the design of the deformable structure of the fine indentation SMA composite.

2 EXPERIMENT

2.1 Materials

The resin used was an epoxy resin of Model AM-8927A from Huibai New Materials Co., Ltd., and the curing agent was AM-8927B curing agent. The mass ratio of epoxy resin to curing agent was 100:30.

The NiTi-based shape memory alloy wire purchased from Beijing Jiyi Electronics Co., Ltd. is a single-pass memory alloy wire with a diameter of 0.6 mm.

2.2 Sample fabrication

First cut the SMA wire into a wire segment of about 500 mm, then use the indentation device, as shown in Figure 2.1, to make the indented SMA wire, and then insert the indented SMA wire into the silicone mold. In the small hole, the silicone mold is placed on the aluminum bracket, and the upper and lower ends are bolted and provided with a certain tension to straighten the SMA wire, as shown in Figure 2.2. Then, the epoxy resin which has been mixed with the curing agent in a certain mass ratio is poured into the mold. The curing process is maintained at 50 °C for 7 h, and after 110 °C post-curing for 3 h, the glass transition temperature of the resin matrix can reach 120 °C. The test piece can be obtained after demolding, as shown in Figure 2.3.

Figure 2.1 Indentation device schematic and physical map

Figure 2.2 Silicone mold and bracket

Figure 2.3 Drawing test specimen

2.3 Drawing test

The drawing test is carried out on the Wance electronic universal testing machine. The wire at one end of the sample is pierced from the bottom hole on the steel drawing bracket and fixed at the drawing end, as shown in Fig. 3.5(a). In order to capture the initial slip point of the indented SMA wire, the laser

displacement sensor of Shanghai Haonai Electronic Technology Co., Ltd. was used to fix the laser displacement sensor on one side of the steel frame and near the wire clamp. Fix a thin foam board for laser positioning, as shown in Figure 3.5(b). The test machine and the laser displacement sensor simultaneously collect data. At the moment when the SMA wire slips, the laser displacement sensor can accurately capture the sudden change of displacement by virtue of its extremely sensitive characteristics, so as to find the initial slip point according to time.

Figure 2.4 Drawing test equipment

The whole experiment was carried out at room temperature with a loading rate of 2 mm/min. The entire experimental procedure is shown in Figure 2.4.

2.4 Capture of the starting slip point

Figure 2.6 shows the experimental data of four samples. The ordinate data is the tensile force collected by the universal testing machine, and the abscissa is the displacement data collected by the laser displacement sensor. Since the experiment is not performed once, the laser displacement sensor has a fixed position, which causes the initial displacement to be different. However, the initial displacement has no effect on the capture of the initial slip point.

Figure 2.5 Drawing test sample force and slip diagram

For sample 1, as shown in Figure 2.5(a), we can see from the figure that the initial slip point is at 56s based on the displacement curve, the corresponding pulling force is 67N. After that, the interface begins to break. When the tensile force reaches 238N, the interface is completely destroyed, and after the tensile force drops to the residual interface strength, the SMA wire is slowly pulled out.

For sample 2, as shown in Figure 2.5(b), we can see from the figure that the initial slip point is at 71s based on the displacement curve, the corresponding pulling force is 72N. After that, the pulling force has a small range fluctuations, then continue to rise, and the amount of slip begins to accelerate. When the tensile force reaches 250N, the interface is completely destroyed.

For sample 3, as shown in Fig. 2.5(c), we can see from the figure that the initial slip point is at 112s based on the displacement curve, the corresponding pulling force is 78N. After that, the rate of increase of displacement increases greatly, and the pulling force is increased. There are also certain fluctuations.

For sample 4, as shown in Fig. 2.5(d), it is made of smooth SMA wire. We can see from the figure that the initial slip point is at 30s based on the displacement curve, the corresponding pulling force is 39N. After that, the rate of increase of displacement increases greatly, and the pulling force is increased. When the tensile force reaches 88N, the interface is completely destroyed.

The tensile forces of the initial slip points and the limit force point of each sample are summarized in Table 2.1.

Table 2.1 Test results data

Sample Number	1	2	3	4
Load of initial slip point (N)	67	72	78	39
Load of limit force point(N)	238	242	253	88

Take the average value of the initial slip points of the three samples made of indented SMA wire, which is 72N, and it can be concluded that within the range of tension of the samples reaching 70-80N, the interface has begun to be damaged and the debonding has begun at the stress concentration. The round SMA wire is smaller than the indentation SMA wire regardless of the initial slip load or the ultimate slip load.

3 STUDY ON BONDING AND SLIDING PROPERTIES OF INDENTED SMA WIRE

When the outer SMA wire is subjected to tension, the interface bonding stress between SMA wire and its surrounding resin is not evenly distributed. At the sample end near to the loading SMA wire, the bonding stress is concentration and the interface will fail first, but then it will maintain a certain bond-slip. With the increase of tensile force, the interface failure area continues to expand, eventually destroying completely, the load is reduced, the SMA wire is slowly pulled out, and a certain load is still needed when pulling out, which fully indicates that there is still a certain residual adhesive strength.

3.1 Bond slip τ -s curve

In order to facilitate the study, the average bond stress τ_u , F is the load at a certain moment, d is the diameter of the SMA wire, l_0 is the length of the SMA wire in the resin, the length of this sample is 50mm, so l_0 is 50mm.

$$\tau_u = \frac{F}{\pi dl_0} \quad (3-1)$$

Due to the structure of the experimental support, the test point of the laser displacement sensing in this experiment has to be taken 10 mm away from the end of the sample. Therefore, the displacement needs to be subtracted from the length of the 10 mm SMA wire and the deformation amount in the stretching stage, so the slip amount s is:

$$s = s_l - s' \quad (3-2)$$

$$s' = \frac{Fl'}{E_f A} \quad (3-3)$$

Where: the displacement measured by the s_l laser displacement sensor, l' is 10mm, and A is the cross-sectional area of the SMA wire. Take the data of sample 1 to establish the bond slip τ -s curve, as shown in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1 Bond slip τ -s curve

3.2 Bond-slip constitutive model

According to the bond slip τ -s curve of Figure 3.1, the curve can be defined in sections.

AB segment, using a quadratic polynomial description

AB is the rising section of the curve. Because of the initial point of slip, the initial sliding bond stress is not zero, the initial slip bond stress is τ_0 , and the maximum bond slip stress is τ_u , point B. The slip amount is s_u , and the quadratic polynomial equation is established as:

$$\frac{\tau - \tau_0}{\tau_u} = C_1 \left(\frac{s}{s_u}\right)^2 + C_2 \left(\frac{s}{s_u}\right) \quad (0 < s \leq s_u) \quad (3-4)$$

After curve fitting, the coefficients $C_1 = 0.4728$ and $C_2 = 0.1879$ were obtained.

BC segment, using a straight line description

The BC segment is a descending curve of the curve, which is described by a straight line. The mathematical expression is:

$$\tau - \tau_u = C_3(s - s_u) \quad (s_u < s \leq s_r) \quad (3-5)$$

Where s_r is the slip amount of point C, and the data is brought to $C_3 = -0.3018$.

CD segment, using a straight line to describe

The CD segment is the residual stage of the SMA wire slip, and the residual strength of the interface remains unchanged for a period of time during the slip. Therefore, the mathematical description is made by a straight line:

$$\tau = \tau_r \quad (s > s_r) \quad (3-6)$$

Another sample is taken and the data obtained from the sample is taken into the resulting constitutive equation and compared with the experimental data, as shown in Figure 3.2:

Figure 3.2 Comparison of τ -s curve experiment and calculated data

It can be seen from Fig 3.2 that the experimental value is in good agreement with the theoretical value. Therefore, the obtained bond-slip constitutive model has certain practicability and can be used as a theoretical analysis method.

4 ANALYSIS OF INTERFACE STRENGTH

4.1 FEM Model

Based on ANSYS software, the solid element model of double cylindrical drawing structure is established in this paper. The diameter of the resin layer is 20mm, the length is 50mm, the SMA wire is 0.6mm, and the length is 54mm, each with a length of 2mm, and increased mesh density near the contact surface, making the shear stress analysis more accurate. The constraint condition is that all the outer wall of the resin layer is fixed. The load was applied at 72 N, which is the initial slip load of the specimen. The shear stress coordinate system is the cylindrical coordinate system. The YZ surface is selected to obtain the shear stress cloud diagram as shown in Figure 4.1. It can be seen that there is obvious stress concentration at the drawing end.

Figure 4.1 Shear stress nephogram

Take a 0.2mm thick resin layer in contact with the SMA wire. The stress cloud diagram is shown in Figure 4.2. The maximum shear stress is 121.88MPa, and it is located on the surface of the resin layer

near the SMA wire. The stress distribution along the length of the cylinder is shown in Figure 4.3(a), it can be seen that the stress concentration occurs at the end close to the load. Another maximum stress along the diameter of the cylindrical end face is shown in Figure 4.3(b). It can be seen that the maximum stress appears near the SMA wire. Outward in the diametrical direction, the stress drops rapidly, and at 0.2 mm, the shear stress is already zero.

Figure 4.2 0.2mm thickness resin layer shear stress nephogram

Figure 4.3 Shear stress along the path

4.2 THEORETICAL ANALYSIS AND NUMERICAL COMPARISON

4.2.1 Theoretical analysis

Yousef Payandeh^[11] et al. derived the formula to obtain the critical failure stress τ_{lim} between the SMA wire and the resin matrix, and the data of this experiment was brought into the formula (4-1) to obtain τ_{lim} of 31.83MPa.

$$\tau_{lim} = \left(\frac{\gamma}{2}\right) [B \sinh(2\gamma s) + C \cosh(2\gamma s)] \sigma_p \quad (4-1)$$

$$\gamma = \sqrt{\frac{1}{A(1+\nu_m)} \left(\frac{S_f}{S_m} + \frac{E_m}{E_f}\right)} \quad (4-2)$$

$$A = -0.25 + b^2 \frac{2b^2 \ln\left(\frac{b}{a}\right) - b^2 + a^2}{2(b^2 - a^2)^2} \quad (4-3)$$

$$B = -\frac{S_f E_f}{S_f E_f + S_m E_m} \quad (4-4)$$

$$C = \operatorname{csch}(2\gamma s) - B \tanh(\gamma s) \quad (4-5)$$

$$\sigma_p = \frac{F}{\pi a^2} \quad (4-6)$$

$$s = \frac{L}{2a} \quad (4-7)$$

Among them, E_f and E_m are the elastic modulus of the SMA wire and the resin matrix; a , b respectively refer to the radius of the SMA wire and the radius of the resin; ν_m is the Poisson's ratio of the resin matrix. $S_f = \pi a^2$ and $S_m = \pi (b^2 - a^2)$ are the cross-sectional areas of the fiber and the resin. L is the length of the double cylindrical test piece, A , B , C , γ are the parameters related to the size and material properties of the test piece, and F is the critical failure load of the test piece obtained from the force-displacement curve. The initial slip load is used in this paper.

4.2.2 Comparative analysis of results

In summary, the initial slip shear stress and the ultimate shear stress results are shown in the Table 4.1.

Table 4.1 Shear stress results

	Experimental average shear strength value	Numerical simulation value	Theoretical calculation
Shear Stress of initial slip point(MPa)	0.7675	121.88	31.83
Shear Stress of limit force point(MPa)	2.59	413.59	110.52

Since the experimental value uses the calculation method of the average shear stress, in the pull test, the actual shear stress has a phenomenon of end stress concentration, so the experimental value are smaller than the theoretical calculation value and the numerical simulation value. The result of finite element numerical simulation is larger than the theoretical calculation value. Therefore, the use of theoretical calculations or average stress methods in design will make the design more conservative.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this paper, the method of determining the initial slip point during the pull-out test of fine indented SMA wire composites is studied. The bond-slip τ - s curve is obtained, the bond-slip constitutive model is established. Numerical simulation and theoretical calculation were carried out using the initial slip load obtained from the experiment. The initial slip shear stress and ultimate shear stress obtained by the three methods were discussed and compared. The relevant conclusions have a guiding role in guiding the design of SMA-based morphing composite structures.

REFERENCES

- [1] Rogers, C. A., Robertshaw, H. H. Development of a Novel Smart Material. ASME Paper , 1988a:WA/DE-9
- [2] Rogers, C. A., Robertshaw, H. H. Shape Memory Alloy Reinforced Composites. Engineering Science Preprints, Society of Engineering Science ,1988b: 25,ESP25.88027
- [3] J.S.N. Painet, W.M. Jonest, C.A. Rogers. Nitinol Actuator to Host Composite Interfacial Adhesion in Adaptive Hybrid Composites. AIAA-92-240:556-565
- [4] Jonnalagadda K, Kline GE, Sottos NR. Local displacements and load transfer in shape memory alloy composites. Exp Mech., 1997,37(1):78-85
- [5] Eisaku Umezaki. Improvement in separation of SMA from matrix in SMA embedded smart composite. Mater. Sci. Eng. A. 2000,285:363-369
- [6] Lau K T, Tam W Y, Meng X L, Zhou M. Morphological study on twisted NiTi wires for smart composite systems. Materials Letters, 2002,57:364-368

- [7] Smith N A, Antoun G. Improved adhesion between nickel-titanium shape memory Alloy and Polymer matrix via silane coupling agents. *ComPosites:PartA*.2004,35:1307-1312
- [8] B. K. Jang, T. Kishi. Adhesive strength between NiTi fibers embedded in CFRP composite. *Mater. Let.*, 2005,59:1338-1341
- [9] H.C. Man, N.Q. Zhao. Enhancing the adhesive bonding strength of NiTi shape memory alloys by laser gas nitriding and selective etching. *Applied Surface Science*, 2006,253: 1595-1600
- [10] Li-min Zhao, Xue Feng, Xu-jun Mi, Yan-feng Li, Hao-feng Xie, Xiang-qian Yin. The interfacial strength improvement of SMA composite using ZnO with electrochemical deposition method. *Applied Surface Science*, 2014,320: 670–673
- [11] Yousef Payandeh, Fodil Meraghni, Etienne Patoor, Andre Eberhardt. Debonding initiation in a NiTi shape memory wire epoxy matrix composite. Influence of martensitic transformation. *Mater Des* 2010,31:1077-1084